

Lorentz Transformation Derived Directly for a Photon?

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In previous notes, we have focused on obtaining the Lorentz transformation as a spacetime transformation for a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$ at t . The key idea was to impose $x'/t'=v$ which applies to the motion of the particle with rest mass. This approach leads to a 2×2 matrix which contains a parameter b , with units of velocity, which is the same in all frames. If one argues that the 2×2 matrix, which is a transformation of x, t to x', t' , should also hold for a photon because it shares the same spacetime as a particle with rest mass, then $b=c$.

Here, we try to argue that the Lorentz transformation may be derived directly for either a particle with rest mass or a photon because the key idea is how an interval in spacetime appears to people in one frame or another. In other words, one does not need to consider this interval as pertaining to the motion of the object, i.e. to the speed c for a photon or a particle with rest mass moving at v . One is able to use this viewpoint because $x=0, t=0$ transforms to $x'=0, t'=0$ under a matrix transformation. Thus, constant velocity requires an interval in space and time, but even for a photon which moves at speed c there are measurement intervals. One may say that in one frame a measurement is: $x=0$ at t which is a space-time interval from $x=0, t=0$. The question then is what interval will the person in a frame moving with $-v$ see regardless of the c speed of the photon? We argue that t becomes t' , but that $x'=vt'$ should still hold when deriving the Lorentz matrix even for a photon. This result now pertains to a measurement point from $(x=0, t=0)$ or $(x'=0, t'=0)$, not the position of the moving photon because the photon does not move with speed v .

. In the moving frame 0 to t' means the measured point and changed to $x'-0$ given by $x'=vt'$. In a so-called rest frame (from the point of view of measurement) $x=0$ can be measured at $t=0$ or t . Thus, $x=0, t=0$ evolved to $x=0, t$ in terms of measurement, not in terms of the motion of the photon. This has nothing to do with the fact that the photon moves with speed c , one is considering a measurement point from the point $(x=0, t=0)$ which is the same for $(x'=0, t'=0)$. Thus, a rest frame always exists for a measurement point regardless whether one has a particle with rest mass or a photon, we argue. In particular, one may argue that a co-ordinate axes is at rest in one frame and then viewed from a frame moving with $-v$. This approach, which does not require a particle with rest mass at rest yields the Lorentz transformation.

One again obtains a parameter b which may be found by imposing $x/t=c$ and $x'/t'=c$ for a photon as the intervals now pertain to the photon speed. Thus, with a Lorentz transformation, intervals do not necessarily need to pertain to the motion of the object, whether it be a particle with rest mass or a photon. The notion of a photon having the same speed in all frames, however, must be implemented.

Lorentz Transformation for a Particle with Rest Mass

In a number of previous notes, we have considered a spacetime transformation for a particle with a rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$ at t . In a frame moving with $-v$, the particle should satisfy:

$x'/t' = v$ ((1)) because $x=0, t=0$ maps to $x'=0, t'=0$ for a matrix transformation

This leads to:

$$\begin{matrix} | A & g(v) v & | & x=0 & | & ((2)) \\ | B & g(v) & | & |t| \end{matrix}$$

$g(v)$ is a number and so should really be written as $g(v/b)$ where b is a constant with units of velocity. The same constant applies for all frames. So far, $g(v/b)$ is unknown, but if one wishes a modulus of (x, bt) to be invariant, then one cannot use the usual $xx + bbtt$ because for $x=0$ and t small, one could have x', t' large, not allowing for equality. Thus, one seeks a minus sign metric. In other words:

$$\begin{matrix} (x' & t') & | & 1 & 0 & | & x' & | & ((3)) \\ & & | & 0 & -1 & | & |t' \end{matrix}$$

This leads to: $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ ((4))

B is still unknown, but the transformation in ((2)) applies to x, t space. Even though ((2)) was derived for a particle with rest mass, the same x, t space applies to a photon and so we have argued that the matrix of ((2)) should allow for:

$$x/t=c \quad x'/t' = c \quad ((5))$$

As shown in a previous note, this leads to $b=c$.

At this point, a spacetime transformation of a particle with rest mass in a rest frame has been used to obtain the Lorentz transformation in terms of a constant b with velocity units. Then, it has been suggested that a photon's x, bt should also transform according to ((2)), because a photon and particle with rest mass share the same x, t space. This leads to $b=c$. This, however, begs the question: Why does one need to start with a particle with rest mass to obtain ((2))? Why can't one start with a photon?

Moving Frames Viewing Measurement Intervals

In the above section, we focused on x and t describing a particle, whether it be one with rest mass or a photon ($m_0=0$). A moving frame ($-v$) means that there is a velocity in the picture and a constant velocity is linked with:

$$v = \{x_1 - x_2\} / \{t_1 - t_2\} \quad ((6))$$

It was assumed in the above section that x_1 and x_2 should apply to particle/photon positions at t_1 and t_2 . There is nothing wrong with such an assumption, we argue, but this is not the only identification of intervals one may make.

Even for a photon, there are co-ordinate axes with an origin as one measures:

$$x=ct \quad ((7))$$

These co-ordinate axes are at rest in one frame and moving as seen from the frame moving with $-v$. For both frames:

$$(x=0, t=0) \text{ maps to } (x'=0, t'=0) \quad ((8))$$

If one imagines an $x=0, t$ in the co-ordinate axes rest frame, this means there has been an evolution from:

$$(x=0, t=0) \text{ to } (x=0, t) \quad ((9))$$

From the point of view of the person in the frame moving with $-v$, the evolution is:

$$(x'=0, t'=0) \text{ to } (x'=vt', t') \quad ((10))$$

Thus, the notion of a moving frame is not necessarily restricted to the motion of a particle or photon. It can be applied to a measurement respective to $(x=0, t=0)$ or $(x'=0, t'=0)$.

We argue that this is a key idea because one may now derive the Lorentz transformation strictly for a photon which always moves with speed c in a vacuum.

The main idea is to impose:

$$x'=vt' \text{ as done in } ((10))$$

Once this is done, $x=0, t$ is simply a measurement point relative to $(x=0, t=0)$ and a matrix acting $(x=0, bt)$ must yield $x'=vt'$ and $t'=g(v) t$. This is precisely the matrix of $((2))$

Thus, using the ideas of the first section one arrives at:

$$g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((11))$$

without any notion of a particle with rest mass. The rest frame, so to speak, is one in which a particular co-ordinate axes is at rest (i.e. x, t).

As a result, instead of thinking of obtaining the Lorentz transformation from a spacetime transformation of a particle with rest mass at rest at $x=0, t$ and then forcing the transformation to also hold for a photon, one may do the following. One may consider a transformation acting on a measurement point $x=0, t$ relative to $x=0, t=0$ and compare this interval as seen by a frame moving with $-v$. Enforcing:

$$X'x' - bt't' = xx - bb tt \text{ yields } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb} \quad ((12))$$

One may then apply the transformation to a photon $x/t=c, x'/t'=c$ to obtain $c=b$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to derive the Lorentz transformation in previous notes from considerations of a spacetime matrix transformation of a particle with rest mass at rest at $x=0$ at t . In particular, we only focused on the motion of the particle as seen from a frame moving with $-v$. This leads to a Lorentz transformation including $g(v) = 1 / \sqrt{1 - vv/bb}$, where b is a constant with units of velocity. We then had to apply the transformation to a photon, $x/t=c$, $x'/t'=c$ to obtain $c=b$.

Here, we ask: Why cannot one only use a photon alone to derive the Lorentz transformation? We argue that one can. Although it is possible to consider x_1-x_2 and t_1-t_2 intervals as applying to the motion of the center-of-mass of a particle with rest mass or a photon, there are other intervals possible. In particular, there is a measurement interval. Given that $(x=0, t=0)$ transforms via a matrix to $(x'=0, t'=0)$, an $(x=0, t)$ may be compared to $(x=0, t=0)$ to yield an x and t interval. In the moving frame, this same interval is: $(x'=vt', t')$ relative to $(x'=0, t'=0)$. In other words, the so-called rest frame may be a frame in which a particular co-ordinate axes set is at rest. In the moving frame, a measurement interval would be different. This idea replaces the particle at rest, but $x'/t'=v$ still applies and allows one to obtain the Lorentz transformation matrix in terms of $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1 - vv/bb}$, where b is a constant with units of velocity. One then needs to apply this to a photon: $x/t=c$, $x'/t'=c$ to show that $c=b$. Thus, it is really photon behaviour with c being the same in all frames (vacuum) which is required to obtain the Lorentz transformation, in addition to effects of v on measurement intervals.